

THE IMPORTANCE OF CREATIVE APPROACH IN DEVELOPING ORGANIZATIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS

Karimova Jahona

1st stage master of Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10810142>

Abstract. *The creative approach of Primary School teachers is aimed at giving students the opportunity to see the basis of the problem through in-depth study of the instructional material.*

Keywords: *creative, creation, science, contemplation, fitness, ability, contemplation, training, orientation, intellectual.*

Аннотация. *Творческий подход учителей начальных классов направлен на то, чтобы дать возможность учащимся увидеть, корень проблемы посредством углубленного изучения учебного материала.*

Ключевые слова: *креатив, творчество, научный, мышления, деятельность, способность, мысль, образование, позванивать, интеллектуюал.*

Creativity - (lexically derived from the Latin words "to create, build" and used in the sense of "creativity and creativity") to search for solutions to scientific problems in the educational material, to solve them in a unique, creative way a qualitative description of the number of actions aimed at According to most psychologists, creativity is the ability to see things differently, to find unique solutions to problems.

In primary and secondary education, the creative approach focuses on enabling students to see the root of the problem through in-depth study of the learning material. In the process of higher education, the creative approach is the focus of the student's scientific-creative thinking on the solution of the system of certain fields in the field of specialization, and it is expressed in the application of individual forms of creative work. Creativity approach develops intellectual-creative abilities in pupils and students. prepares to defend his creative product, diploma work, master's thesis in front of the team based on evidence and logic. The integrated system of creative education and self-education is based on the principles of heuristic teaching.

Strengthening the needs of future elementary teachers to engage in scientific research in higher educational institutions and training high-potential mature specialists capable of solving personal and professional problems by developing their research competencies is a system of higher pedagogical education. is one of the important tasks ahead. Research activities always require a creative approach. It focuses on students' self-realization, identification and manifestation of their inner potential. The learner works as hard as the creator on the research. And this work attracts with its novelty, creative application, unusualness. The content of the research work and its technical equipment depends on the student's imagination - he chooses the information that he considers important in revealing the topic, carries out the equipment of the research based on the scheme, table, scientific method. According to the researchers, if a high coefficient of intelligence is supplemented with high indicators of creativity, a person will achieve great success in professional and managerial activities, and develop creative and research abilities. People with higher IQs and lower levels of creativity are less likely to achieve great success, even though they fully master technology. That is, if a teacher who knows his subject well does not show creative qualities, his work results will not be high enough. The formation of professional qualities of students is directly connected with the activity of creative activity of the individual during the teaching process. The most important task of modern teaching in the higher education system is to

create favorable conditions for the formation of students' awareness of their profession. Creative activity is an activity that requires long preparation, erudition, and abilities. Creative activity is the basis of human activity, the source of all material and spiritual wealth.

The key to the successful creative activity of the future teacher is the timely selection of the necessary information. Needs are the main factors driving the generation of creative ideas and hypotheses. The quality of this demand is determined by the availability of knowledge and skills.

Due to the relevance of competence-oriented approaches in education, the terms "competence", "competence", "basic competences" are increasingly used and widespread in the discussion of issues related to new qualities of education. In the pedagogical community, the process of understanding competences and competencies, which of them are considered basic (universal), and the methods of their formation and evaluation is gaining momentum, intense discussions on clarifying these concepts continue. Therefore, today there are many definitions and interpretations of these concepts. M. Makhmudov describes creative activity as follows: creative activity is a heuristic activity, the essence of which is to quickly understand the problem, to understand the main idea, the essence of the concept, to quickly find a method of action. Such activity is characterized by high enthusiasm, great interest of the subject in the object. The work of V.S.Kuzin, A.N.Leontyev, A.V.Petrovsky, V.S.Rubenstein, M.G.Yaroshevsky and other scientists became a methodical basis for studying the problem of activating their creativity during learning activities in order to form the professional skills of future teachers.

The essence of the concepts of "competence" and "professional competence". In the conditions of market relations, resistance to strong competition, which takes priority in the labor market, requires every specialist to have professional competence and to increase it consistently. So what is competence? What qualities are reflected in the basis of professional competence? What qualities of competence should a teacher be able to highlight in himself? In this place, we will talk about these and related ideas. "Competence" (eng. "competence" - "ability") - effective use of theoretical knowledge in activity, the ability to demonstrate high-level professional qualifications, skill and talent 4 The concept of "competence" entered the field of education as a result of psychological scientific research. From a psychological point of view, competence is "how a specialist behaves in unconventional situations, unexpected situations, engages in communication, takes a new way in relations with opponents, performs ambiguous tasks, uses conflicting information, consistently develops and ownership of a plan of action in complex processes. Professional competence does not mean the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills by a specialist, but the acquisition of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent direction. Also, competence requires constant enrichment of professional knowledge, learning new information, understanding important social requirements, finding new information, processing it and being able to use it in one's work.

Not so long ago, the concept of "creative pedagogy" began to be used in modern pedagogy. However, the need to find innovative and creative approaches to the teaching process ensured the formation of "Creative pedagogy" as an independent subject among pedagogical disciplines. The basics of this subject include the history of pedagogy, general and professional pedagogy and psychology, teaching methodology of special subjects, educational technology and professional ethics.

Not so long ago, the concept of "creative pedagogy" began to be used in modern pedagogy. However, the need to find innovative and creative approaches to the teaching process ensured the formation of "Creative pedagogy" as an independent subject among pedagogical disciplines. The

basis of this subject is the history of pedagogy, general and professional pedagogy, and methodological ideas of such disciplines as psychology, teaching methodology of special subjects, educational technology, and professional ethics. The general principles of the science of "creative pedagogy" serve to create the necessary conditions for the professional development of specialists, including future specialists.

The professional growth and development of a person as a specialist is manifested as a process according to its essence. Professional maturity is an important period of human ontogeny, starting with professional growth and development ideas (ages 14-17) and ending with professional activity (ages 55-60). The formation and development of a creative person depends on the mutual compatibility of changes in his inner and outer world, socio-economic conditions, and human ontogeny - from birth to the end of his life, the content of activity that requires continuity and succession.

Creativity (lat., ing. "create" - creation, "creative" - creator) is the creative ability of an individual that describes the readiness to produce new ideas and is part of talent as an independent factor. Pedagogical creativity is the ability of a pedagogue to create new ideas that serve to ensure the effectiveness of the educational process, as well as to positively solve existing pedagogical problems, unlike traditional pedagogical thinking.

The creativity of the pedagogue in professional activity is manifested in various forms. They are:

- ✓ Preparation of regulatory documents (DTS, curriculum and plans for academic subjects); Creation of educational resources (textbook, teaching-methodical and methodical guide, recommendation letter, dictionary, encyclopedia, atlas, workbook, etc.);
- ✓ Preparation of educational process and projects of spiritual and educational works;
- ✓ Formation of educational information, control and test assignments;
- ✓ Organizing the educational process in an interesting, lively, energetic manner;
- ✓ Successfully conduct scientific research;
- ✓ Active participation in scientific and methodical conferences, giving speeches;
- ✓ Publication of scientific, scientific-methodical and methodical works;
- ✓ Submission of periodic reports, certification.

The effective organization of professional activity by the teacher in these forms depends on the level of his creativity.

In the process of creative activity, the ability of a person to overcome many obstacles, to strain his mental and physical forces, and to consciously regulate his actions before reaching the goal he has set for himself is called will. In the educational process and creative activity, in the formation of professional qualities of students, many things depend on the will, the ability to overcome difficulties. Volitional influence is a conscious action, which can be motivated by various needs. The best way to help in the training of future vocational education teachers is to acquire preparatory work skills in technical and technological processes, project activities and specific professional knowledge.

Thus, based on the above considerations, we concluded that it is possible to develop this type of cognitive activity in learners in a goal-oriented manner regarding the research of perception and perception. We believe that a person's intuition and perception depend to a large extent on the intellectual aspect, the level and content of a person's knowledge, the person's instructions, interests, general orientation and previous experience, and professional creativity.

REFERENCES

1. Makhmudov NM Teacher speech culture. Textbook. - Tashkent, National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, 2007. - 185 p.
2. Muslimov NA and others. Basics of pedagogical competence and creativity / - Tashkent, 2015. - 120 pages.
3. Yeibullayev NR and others. Pedagogy//Handbook for higher educational institutions. - Tashkent, UzMU, 2005. - 176 p.
4. Yeoziyev E. Psychology. - Tashkent, Teacher, 1994. - 224 p.
5. Khalikov AA Development of pedagogical skills of future teachers in higher educational institutions. // Monograph. - Economy Finance. - Tashkent. - 2015.-435 p.